

PROSPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION SERVICE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article clarifies the terms of service market on the basis of scientific research of foreign and national researchers, classifies the features of services, identifies areas and opportunities for the use of service activities in Uzbekistan. Furthermore, based on the dynamic range of services in 2013-2023, the laws of change of indicators were identified and the level of change of indicators until 2025 was forecasted on the basis of the identified laws.*

Keywords: *Service market, modernization, services sector, financial services, higher education services.*

In the context of modernization of the country, one of the most pressing issues today is to provide services to the population, improve their living standards and solve the problem of employment. By providing various services, firstly, the needs of the population in services will be met, secondly, the problem of employment of the unemployed will be solved, and thirdly, the living standards of the population will improve and incomes will increase. . Therefore, the provision of affordable services to the population, employment and improvement of living standards of the population within the chosen topic is one of the most important areas of scientific research.

In the theoretical study of the service sector, it is expedient to pay attention, first of all, to the meaning of such terms as "service", "service market". The term "services" is interpreted differently by scholars in the economic literature from different perspectives. Within the framework of these terms, many foreign and domestic scientists have conducted theoretical research. F. Kotler, a well-known scholar, describes service as follows: Service is any activity that one party may offer to another.¹

S.N.Korobkova describes the sphere of services as follows: "The sphere of services is the sphere of the economy in which goods are created, which have a

¹ Kotler, F., Marketing management. Ex press-course. 2nd ed. / Per. s angl. under red. Bojuk S. G. SPb .: Peter, 2006. -464 p

beneficial effect on the process of creation. Labor in the service sector is not expressed in the form of material goods ".²

. According to the definition given by G.A.Avanesova, L.P.Voronkova, V.I.Maslov, A.I.Frolov: It is the sphere of industrial practice and social interaction of the organizers of useful activities, the competition of producers of goods and products.³

Modernization of the service sector is a very complex social and economic phenomenon. It is difficult to make strategic decisions on modernization of the service sector without an in-depth study of these complex socio-economic processes. Because in modernization, social change does not take place spontaneously, mechanically. On the contrary, it is a very complex process, in which socio-economic changes and innovations in society sometimes take place openly, sometimes secretly. World practice has shown that in the process of transition from traditional societies to modern societies, the living standards of the population are sharply affected, stratification among the population and the balance of social justice is disturbed. Some promising industries and sectors will also face their own challenges over time. Therefore, today, modernization is one of the most important, yet one of the most complex, critical scientific paradigms. Probably for this reason, clear and perfect methods for implementing the process of modernization of the service sector have not yet been developed.

The research of economists L.N.Maniskaya and B.M.Jukov on the modernization of service organizations is one of the most important scientific achievements in this area.⁴

They developed modernization models in service enterprises and showed both external and internal factors influencing it. The development of modernization models in service enterprises plays an important role in the development of the industry, but does not allow the development and definition of a single approach. Modernization is also needed to develop the service sector and strengthen its position in the national economy. Therefore, a method of modernization of the service sector should be developed.

² Korobkova S.N. *Servisnaya deyatelnost. Uchebnoe posobie*. Edited by VK Romanovicha Publishing House -SPb Peter 2006.

³ Avanesova G.A., Voronkova L.P., Maslov V.I., Frolov A.I. *Tourism, hospitality, service. Glossary*. Pod red. L.P.Voronkovoy. -M.: Aspekt Press, 2002. -367 p

⁴ Manitskaya L.N., Zhukov B.M. *Modernization predpriyatiy sphere of service: conceptual model and instrumental means*. // «Modern problems of science and education» No3,2011. <https://scienceeducation.ru/ru/article/view?id=4711>.

Modernization of the service sector is very different from the modernization of the agricultural and industrial sectors of the economy. For example, the modernization of agriculture involves the uninterrupted and sustainable supply of food to the population, increasing the productivity of land resources, maintaining the ecological balance or a sharp increase in the export potential of the industry. Modernization of industrial sectors also involves the most efficient use of non-renewable resources. Modernization of the service sector will create the following opportunities:

- increases the range of services;
- increases the volume of services;
- improves the quality of services;
- Increases service speed.

There is a peculiarity of modernization of the service sector. It leads to a reduction in the number of employees employed in some sectors of the service sector, while in others it provides employment to the population. For example, new technologies in medicine make it possible to simultaneously determine a patient's blood pressure, heart rate, and blood composition. In this case, the patient does not need to see another doctor for his disease. This means that there will be a reduction in the number of specialists in this field. In the field of education, the intensification of the modernization process will create new jobs. The introduction of modernization in the field of education will change the annual workload of each teacher in educational institutions as a result of updating the curriculum and adapting it to the requirements of world standards. Modernization in education gives teachers special time to work on themselves, use new resources, find new pedagogical technologies. This will create new jobs in this area, further improving the quality of education. Therefore, it is not expedient to take the modernization of the service sector as a whole. It should be viewed from the perspective of employment as much as possible. This will create new jobs in this area, further improving the quality of education. Therefore, it is not expedient to take the modernization of the service sector as a whole. It should be viewed from the perspective of employment as much as possible. This will create new jobs in this area, further improving the quality of education. Therefore, it is not expedient to take the modernization of the service sector as a whole. It should be viewed from the perspective of employment as much as possible.

One of the important innovations is the provision of academic and financial autonomy. The right of universities to academic freedom, self-governance, and freedom of research and teaching was enshrined at the level of constitutional guarantee. Today, academic and financial autonomy has been granted to 40 universities. At the

same time, the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation is given the right to expand the list in agreement with the Republican Council for Higher Education and the Ministry of Economy and Finance. Providing academic and financial autonomy allows universities to independently decide on issues such as the approval of curricula and programs, qualification requirements, determining the duration and cost of education, introducing part-time, distance, and evening forms of education, implementing academic mobility, opening new and closing existing educational directions and specialties, etc. These measures have expanded autonomy and drastically reduced state administrative management.

Ensuring the integration of higher education, science, and innovation is also a key task of modern reforms. The concept of “University 3.0” which involves a close connection between education, science, innovation, and the commercialization of research results in higher educational institutions, is being implemented in the country’s universities. As a result, the scientific potential of universities has reached 40%, and the number of articles in the Scopus and Web of Science databases has reached 3,574. By the end of 2023, the volume of commercialization of research results by universities and scientific organizations amounted to 270.6 billion soums, and 17 spin-off companies specializing in scientific-intensive products were created.

Significant attention is paid to improving the infrastructure and material-technical base of universities. The capacity of university buildings increased from 274,072 in 2016 to 395,433 in 2024. The level of dormitory coverage for students wishing to live there reached **52%** in 2023 (28% in 2019). Conditions are also being created for the construction of new dormitory capacities based on public-private partnerships.

In conclusion, the work on improving the higher education sector continues today. Among the main implemented measures, the following directions should be noted:

Firstly, measures are being taken to improve the quality of training specialists with higher education. During the first half of 2024, the authorized body in the field of higher education developed and approved 183 qualification requirements for bachelor’s degree programs, taking into account the programs of universities included in the TOP-300. Thirty-eight educational programs from six universities underwent international accreditation. Additionally, to deepen the ongoing reforms in the education sector and organize the activities of educational institutions based on advanced foreign practices, the Project Office “Center for Projects in the Field of Education” was created. This project office is tasked with enhancing the personnel potential in the education sector and raising the quality of educational services to

international standards. As part of improving the quality of education, the Project Office is conducting systematic measures. In particular, this year, bachelor's degree programs have been optimized by 40% (from 306 to 183), and master's degree specialties by 15% (from 625 to 528). The issue of optimizing deans' offices and other administrative structures through the digitization of the educational process in universities is being worked on.

Secondly, the relationship between higher and professional educational institutions is being strengthened, which contributes to the continuity of education. The subjects of the first and second years of university will be integrated with technical schools. Within the framework of educational reforms, it is planned to bring technical school diplomas in line with international standards. In particular, it is planned to issue diplomas corresponding to the international classifier to those who graduated from technical schools with good grades. Additionally, it is planned for students in technical schools to acquire sufficient professional qualifications for continuing their education at universities. Consequently, technical school graduates will have the opportunity to continue their education at the university from the second or third year.

Thirdly, employers are actively involved in the process of training highly qualified specialists. To this end, qualification standards for more than 5,000 professions are being developed. On the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Qualifications Development Institute will be created to develop the necessary qualification requirements in cooperation with employers.

In some applied areas of higher education, employers actively join the educational process. For example, in engineering education, based on the "industry – enterprise – university" chain, each university will be assigned an industrial partner. Engineering universities plan to open departments at corresponding partner enterprises and implement dual education. These departments will be an excellent place for combining theory with practice. In turn, partner enterprises will directly participate in training future personnel.

In conclusion, reforms in the higher education sector will create a healthy competitive atmosphere in the educational services market, implement advanced higher education standards, raise the content of higher education to a qualitatively new level, and establish a system for training highly qualified personnel. . This will create new jobs in this area, further improving the quality of education. Therefore, it is not expedient to take the modernization of the service sector as a whole. It should be viewed from the perspective of employment as much as possible.

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